

PREDICTING THE COMPRESSION-AFTER-IMPACT PERFORMANCE OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES BASED ON IMPACT RESPONSE

A.R. Brindle¹, X Zhang²

¹Royal Australian Navy, Australia

²Aerospace Engineering Dept, School of Engineering, Cranfield University, Cranfield, Bedfordshire, MK43 0AL, Unite Kingdom

xiang.zhang@cranfield.ac.uk

SUMMARY

The aim of this work is to assess a published method [1] that proposes to use only limited impact test coupons to establish the damage tolerance performance of carbon-epoxy composites. Transverse stiffness of impacted plates measured by quasi-static load tests was used to relate to the compression-after-impact (CAI) strength. Results were compared with the CAI strength obtained by standard test method, which requires substantial amount of test coupons and are sensitive to the coupon size and boundary conditions. The equivalence of quasi-static load test and low-velocity impact tests in terms of the critical and maximum impact forces was established; therefore the critical impact force to initiate impact damage can be predicted by testing or FE modelling under quasi-static loading. The work is meaningful in the development of a suitable test programme using limited test coupons. Potentially this method may also solve the size effect problem due to different sample dimensions and boundary conditions leading to its application to the damage tolerance assessment of large structural components.

Keywords: damage tolerance, compression after impact, low velocity impact, quasi-static loading, stiffness reduction

INTRODUCTION

Compression-after-impact (CAI) remains an area of concern for structural designers due to the possibility of strength reduction by damage undetectable by visual inspections. Impact and CAI tests are time and material consuming and the results are largely limited to the material configuration and specific support condition. An alternative approach named the “Composite Structure Impact Performance Assessment Program (CSIPAP)” has been proposed [1] aiming at providing a more efficient tool for damage tolerance assessment of composite structures. This method uses the ratio of pristine to damaged coupon stiffness to determine the CAI strength and damage tolerance performance [2]. In [1-2] this stiffness ratio is represented by the so-called “ratio of contact duration” or “coefficient of restitution (COR)”, which was obtained by either measuring the contact history of impacted plates at undamaged and damaged conditions or calculation of the effective stiffness of impacted plate. The purpose of the CSIPAP is to characterise the impact performance or damage resistance of a composite material and verify its validity through parametric analysis. By a modified approach to the classic spring mass model,

the CSIPAP method takes account of the pristine and damaged structural stiffness of the test coupon and impact fixture [1]. During a subcritical impact (an elastic event in which the critical force is not attained) the COR is a constant value; however once impact energy passes a threshold and damage is initiated the COR decreases rapidly as delamination and matrix fracture occur [1]. However, a direct comparison of this new method with the CAI method is not yet available in the open literature.

In terms of efforts in testing and modelling, quasi-static load (QSL) testing is advantageous over the low-velocity impact test, if one can assume that the influence of inertia may be ignored in the low-velocity regime. There are several benefits in QSL testing as both the damage initiation and propagation are more easily observed. In addition, target deflection and maximum contact force can be more accurately measured and controlled [3-4]. Furthermore, conducting a QSL test using the impact test target assembly prior to impact testing is recommended practice as it allows analysis of elastic behaviour, damage initiation and failure propagation characteristics in response to an applied force [1]. Using identical support fixture and impactor in the static and impact tests, QSL test allows contact force to be determined thereby estimating the threshold impact energy corresponding to the critical impact force and first failure.

This project aims to progress the work in [1] by correlating impact-induced stiffness reduction with the CAI strength. Low velocity impact, QSL and CAI tests were conducted in IM7/Cytec 977-3 laminate. The main objectives are:

- 1) to perform quasi-static load and low-velocity impact tests and compare the results in terms of the critical and maximum impact forces and transverse stiffness;
- 2) to assess the residual compressive performance of impact damaged coupons;
- 3) to assess the ability of the CSIPAP method to determine damage tolerance.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material properties and test coupons

Test material was unidirectional pre-preg tape Cytec 977-3 toughened epoxy resin reinforced by IM7 carbon fibres. Ply mechanical properties were obtained from [5] as: $E_{11} = 162$ GPa, $E_{22} = 8.34$ GPa, $G_{12} = 4.96$ GPa, longitudinal tensile strength (0°) $X_t = 2275$ MPa, longitudinal compressive strength (0°) $X_c = 1680$ MPa, transverse tensile strength (90°) $Y_t = 64$ MPa, interlaminar shear strength $S = 121$ MPa, Poisson's (major) ratio $\nu_{12} = 0.27$. Interlaminar fracture toughness $G_{IC} = 320$ J/m² (DCB test) and $G_{IIC} = 580$ J/m² (ENF test).

A 500 x 560 mm composite panel was produced and 15 test coupons of 4" x 6" (101.6 x 152.4 mm) were cut using a diamond-coated saw. The stacking sequence was a [-45/0/45/90]_{4S} quasi isotropic, mid plane symmetric, 32 ply lay-up with a nominal ply thickness of 0.125 mm producing a coupon of 4 mm nominal thickness. A hand lay-up was used with the panel being debulked every four plies under vacuum and at a temperature of 30°C. The debulking or compacting of the plies ensures that air and volatiles are removed between plies minimising the likelihood of the formation of voids in the laminate. The use of an elevated temperature during debulking aids adhesion between plies.

Ply orientation and properties were inputted into a laminate analysis software named COALA. Calculated membrane equivalent engineering elastic constants are: $E_x = 60.85$ GPa, $E_y = 60.85$ GPa, $G_{xy} = 23.28$ GPa and Poisson's ratios $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx} = 0.31$. Calculated bending equivalent engineering elastic constants are: $E_x = 63.51$ GPa, $E_y = 51.49$ GPa, $G_{xy} = 24.46$ GPa and Poisson's ratios $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx} = 0.37$.

Impact and quasi-static load (QSL) testing

Impact testing was conducted using a Rosand instrumented falling weight impact test rig (Type 5). The instrumentation system comprises a load cell detecting the impact force and an optical sensor recording the impact velocity. The force vs. time history is measured by a piezoelectric transducer linked to a buffer that continuously records data. The impact tester prevents any second strike via a pneumatic catching mechanism. Impact damage was measured by ultrasound C-scanning; through thickness images were produced by the Olympus C-scanner time-of-flight image with details of the damage morphology caused by impact.

Prior to impact testing one pristine test coupon was tested to failure by QSL. Following low-velocity impact tests at 10, 15, 20 and 30 J, these impact-damaged coupons were QSL tested to failure. This series of tests was performed using an INSTRON 8500 (model 8031) digital controlled 50 kN hydraulic load machine. The indenter is placed in a support fixture and mounted in the fixed upper crosshead of the INSTRON load machine. Both the indenter and support fixture conform to the Boeing Impact standard as summarized in [6] and were also used in the impact testing. During all QSL and impact testing coupon edges were supported at all four edges close to the simply supported condition. In accordance with the ASTM standard [4] indentation force is applied by slowly pressing a displacement controlled hemispherical indenter into the surface of a supported coupon; a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min was used until the Mean Static Ultimate Load (MSUL) was achieved in the test coupon.

CAI testing

Eight coupons were compressed to failure in order to develop residual compressive strength data. All tests were conducted using a 600 kN Avery hydraulic load machine. Coupons were inserted in the compression rig and fixture screws were sufficiently torqued to ensure the specimen was able to slide in the anti-buckling guides but out-of-plane movement was prevented. The coupon's loaded edges were fully clamped. The fixture was placed between the flat platens of the Avery machine and compressive force was applied in line with the 0° fibres while load and displacement data were recorded. The coupon was loaded until a maximum force was reached and then subsequently dropped to around 30% (indicating failure had occurred), whereby the test was terminated before further distortion of the coupon could mask the true failure mode and location [7]. Force and crosshead displacement were recorded at 10 Hz resulting in approximately 1000 data points prior to failure.

In order to ensure the application of pure compressive loading and to assess the presence of any bending or twist in the test coupon at failure, five strain gauges were bonded to a coupon that was impacted at 30J and suffered significant delamination. The recorded strain data has been utilised to determine the presence of bending during the compression test and provide an estimate of the surface strain at failure at the impact location. The sign of the calculated bending indicates the direction in which the bending

is occurring. In accordance with [7] a rapid divergence of the strain readings on opposite faces indicates the onset of panel instability due to global or local buckling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact and quasi-static load (QSL) testing

Figure 1 shows the measured impact force vs. time histories, which are filtered traces using the Impacqt software. Several filter tools are available within the software, however the finite impulse response (FIR) filter is considered the best available as components of all frequencies are delayed by an equivalent amount resulting in a stable filter producing minimum amount of distortion [8].

Figure 1. Filtered impact force vs. time histories for 5 – 30 J impacts.

The QSL tests display similar characteristics of force-displacement relation and the critical impact force (first drop in the curve) and the maximum (ultimate) force are comparable to the impact tests within a narrow margin (Figure 2). The point of damage initiation is more easily observed in the QSL force vs. displacement plot than even the filtered impact force-time history. Hysteresis loop is recorded in the low-velocity impact test data, whereas the QSL testing was terminated after the MSUL failure occurred. It is recommended that any future QSL tests should release the load from the test coupon immediately after the MSUL failure occurs and record the relaxation in order to assess the hysteresis and subsequently the dissipated energy.

Figure 2. Comparison of static and impact force vs. displacement relations.

Evaluation of transverse stiffness from QSL testing

Stiffness values of pristine and damaged coupons were determined by the QSL test data and the results were used in the CSIPAP analysis. A contact load vs. displacement relation by QSL testing is shown at Figure 3. As referred in [1-2], two load drops, at the Mean Static Failure Load (MSFL) and Mean Static Ultimate Load (MSUL), characterise the load versus displacement curve. Once the initial contact is made a changing stiffness (apparent in the change in slope in Figure 3) is evident up to 0.6 mm displacement. This initial nonlinear stiffness value can be attributed to contact stresses between the indenter and the coupon, and an indentation is created in the coupon surface. Once specimen is indented further contact stresses spread out and the indentation stops [3]. After this initial nonlinear contact, a stable slope is established until the MSFL value is reached indicating the first failure. Following the MSFL the coupon “reloads”; after this a second change in the slope is apparent as the coupons stiffness has been altered by the first failure. The gradient values for pristine and impact damaged coupons tested by QSL provides the “effective transverse stiffness” k_s and k_d for the pristine and impact damaged coupons as discussed in [2]. Using eq. (1) from [1] the absorbed energies by the QSL coupons at MSFL and MSUL are 4.49 and 25.94 J, respectively. However, the energy dissipated by these failures was not captured by the QSL testing.

$$E = \sum_k \left[(d_j - d_i) \cdot \left(\frac{F_i + F_j}{2} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

Theoretical values of the transverse stiffness of a circular coupon in support fixture were proposed in [1]. However the agreement with the measured is poor [9]. Consequently, in this study QSL test result was used to calculate the stiffness for use in the CSIPAP analysis. Using the load vs. displacement curve in Figure 3, data region in the region between the initial nonlinear contact and the MSFL point has been conducted to estimate the transverse stiffness of the test coupons and support fixture. The gradient of the slope is taken as the k_s value (e.g. 2.76 MN/m in this case). Using the energy balance approach and the force-displacement relation gives the threshold impact energy of 6 J [6].

Figure 3. Quasi-static contact force vs. displacement relation of a pristine coupon.

Residual Compressive Strength

Uniaxial compression tests were performed on impact damaged coupons. Test coupon was supported by an anti-buckling guide during the compression test to prevent global buckling. The desired failure mode is the one in which the failure passes through the impact damage area. Unacceptable failures are those attributed to loading introduced by the support fixture, edge support conditions, and coupon instability (global buckling).

Compressive strength of undamaged coupons was calculated using the Tsai-Hill initial ply failure criterion; it predicts a first-ply failure stress of 629.9 MPa that equals to an applied load of 252 kN. The results of this calculation have been used to normalize the experimentally determined CAI strength to generate the strength retention curve.

The failure mode and location of coupon compression tests were recorded in accordance with [7]. With the exception of the pristine coupon, each coupon failed due to local buckling at the impact damage with kink bands observable in each case. However, edge failure was encountered when a pristine coupon was compressed, which was not used to normalise residual compressive strength values [7]. The failure stress was 398.65 MPa when the edge failure occurred; this is considerably lower than the theoretically calculated pristine failure value (629.9 MPa). Failure of a pristine coupon at the unsupported region close to the top loading plate has been previously reported [10].

CSIPAP method

In accordance with the CSIPAP method [1] a series of subcritical and supercritical impacts were conducted in order to obtain the impact contact duration for pristine and damaged coupons over a range of impact energies. Contact duration was determined using a MATLAB code, by which the duration of impactor-target contact was calculated from recorded force-time history. Impact damaged coupons were then QSL tested to determine the post damage structural stiffness. Based on the transverse stiffness values, contact duration was also calculated according to method in [11], which is discussed below when eq. (2) is presented.

Figure 4 shows the force-time history of an initial 5J subcritical impact (subscript 0), a damaging 30J impact and a subsequent (second) 5J subcritical impact (subscript D). Comparison of the two subcritical impact events confirms the stiffness reduction caused by the delamination by 30J impact, which is manifested by the reduction in the peak

force (in subcritical D) and the increased contact duration. The increase in the contact duration of the second subcritical impact (after a 30 J supercritical impact) is attributed to the degradation of the transverse stiffness of the test coupon. Results of other sequential impact tests are included in [6].

Figure 4. Force–time histories 5 J subcritical and 30 J supercritical impacts.

In the CSIPAP method [1] the ratio of transverse stiffness (i.e. normalised stiffness) is represented by the ratio of contact duration of two subcritical tests: a subcritical impact after a supercritical impact (D) and an initial subcritical impact (0) on pristine coupon. In this work, these data were determined by QSL tests as described below.

Figure 5 shows that in the QSL tests the indenter tip was displaced 6 mm through the coupon thickness direction. This ensured MSUL was achieved in each test case. However, additional failure data were not record as fibres were broken while the coupon deformed and placed the fibres under tension. Prior to and after the MSUL failure event each coupon suffered matrix and fibre crushing and breakage significantly greater than that encountered during impact test. In order to obtain an accurate stiffness value of the damaged coupons, representative of that during the impact testing, data between 0.5 and 2 mm were taken as k_d (Figure 6). This is to ensure that contact stresses between the indenter and coupon during indentation and any damage additional to the delamination inflicted by the original impact test do not influence the post impact transverse stiffness estimate. These measured stiffness values are given in Table 1.

Figure 5 QSL test load and displacement (0 – 6 mm).

Figure 6 QSL test load and displacement (0.5 – 2 mm).

Table 1 Structural stiffness measured by QSL tests

Impact Energy (J)	0	10	15	20	30
Structural Stiffness (MN/m)	2.819	1.929	1.667	1.607	0.956
	(k_0)	(k_d)	(k_d)	(k_d)	(k_d)

The experimentally determined residual compressive strength can be directly compared to the ratio of pristine to damaged contact duration in the form of the strength retention curve. Using a modified spring-mass model, e.g. [11], elastic impact contact duration is:

$$t = \pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{k_0}} \quad (2)$$

where m is impactor mass and k_0 the effective transverse stiffness of pristine laminate and support fixture. Therefore the contact duration ratio can be related to the ratio of pristine to damaged stiffness as [2]:

$$\frac{t_0}{t_d} = \frac{\pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{k_0}}}{\pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{k_d}}} = \left(\frac{k_d}{k_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3)$$

Figure 7 shows the stiffness ratios determined by the QSL test (Table 1) and comparison with the contact duration values. As eq. (2) indicates the contact duration is independent of impact energy during an elastic impact event; however the ratio of a pristine to damaged contact duration for an elastic impact is able to closely represent the residual transverse stiffness of the test coupon. The closeness of two sets of experimental data supports the findings in [1] and substantially validates the testing method used in this work. This correlation relationship is most pronounced in the data range 10–20J impact; at 30J impact difference between the stiffness and contact duration ratios is significant,

and both data points deviate from the best fitted curve for the lower impact energy tests. This is probably due to failure mode change from delamination dominating to extensive back surface matrix cracking caused by bending. The latter was substantial resulting in much more reduction in the coupon's effective stiffness.

Figure 7 Comparison of contact duration and stiffness ratios.

Figure 8 shows comparison of residual compressive strength and residual stiffness in terms of contact duration. The strength retention factor (ratio of damaged to undamaged strengths) was calculated by a theoretical compressive strength determined by the Tsai-Hill criterion. The plot shows significant degradation of post-impact performance once critical energy is exceeded and then asymptotic behaviour that characterises a residual compressive strength curve. The loss of residual stiffness is significantly less than the reduction of compressive strength. Despite this the finding supports the use of the contact duration (or the effective transverse stiffness) as a metric for correlating the CAI strength of a composite structure after sustaining damage.

Figure 8 Comparison of residual strength retention and ratio of contact duration.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Quasi-static load testing can determine the critical impact force and threshold impact energy, as well as the effective transverse stiffness of impact damaged coupons; hence reducing the number of test coupons. Contact duration is found to be a useful parameter to represent the strength and stiffness reduction in material after sustaining low-velocity impact damage. In order to closely correlate this parameter to residual compressive strength an experimentally or theoretically determined scaling factor is required. Within the bounds of the material and geometry used in this project, this factor is two. Additional tests are required to establish the validity of this empirical fit.

The use of predicted compressive strength for pristine coupon could influence the results derived (in terms of the normalised CAI strength). A means to obtain a legitimate compressive strength via testing in a pristine coupon could progress the work.

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